

Management of Teacher Quality Improvement in Implementing Student Learning Culture at Integrated Islamic Schools at the Al-Husnayain Mandailing Natal Indonesia Foundation

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the analysis of planning, resource management, implementation and evaluation related to improving the quality of teachers in the implementation of student learning culture at Integrated Islamic Schools at the Al Husnayain Mandailing Natal Indonesia Foundation. Sources of data in this study are Foundation leaders, school principals, teachers. To achieve this goal, researchers used data collection methods with interview techniques, observation and documentation. The data analysis technique is done by reducing the data, presenting the data, and drawing conclusions. Based on field data and analysis of this research, it was found that the Management of Teacher Quality Improvement in the Implementation of Student Learning Culture at the Integrated Islamic School at the Al Husnayain Mandailing Natal Indonesia Foundation was as follows: 1) Planning to improve the quality of teachers in the implementation of student learning culture has been carried out properly according to the education standards of the Integrated Islamic School and according to the Ministry of Education and Culture's curriculum then integrated with the pesantren regulations. Planning in the form of work programs, regulations, regulations, policies, standard operating procedures that have been agreed upon at foundation meetings and school meetings. 2) In the implementation of the organizing function, foundations and school principals demonstrate their democratic nature by giving trust to the curriculum team (division), boarding coaches, student affairs, extracurricular activities, self-development that is formed according to the needs of the school to participate in carrying out tasks mandated by the principal in accordance with the main duties and functions which has been determined in the division of tasks and responsibilities. 3) In the process of implementing teacher quality improvement, all personnel carry out tasks according to work programs such as: implementation of all 12 JSIT standards, further studies, teacher training, teacher and student achievement, implementation of the learning process (lesson plans, evaluation sheets, literacy programs), process learning in the dormitory (mentoring, evaluation evaluation), extracurricular activities (compulsory activities, choice and dormitory activities) 4) The implementation of evaluation of all standards is carried out by the foundation in general and the evaluation of each educational unit and the boarding house is responsible for the principal and the boarder of the dormitory. Regarding the implementation of learning evaluations in class is carried out every day, every week, every month, at the end of the semester which is evaluated by the teacher. implementation of all 12 JSIT standards, further studies, teacher training, teacher and student achievement, implementation of the learning process (lesson plans, evaluation sheets, literacy programs), the learning process in the dormitory (mentoring, assessment evaluation), extracurricular activities (mandatory, optional and boarding activities) 4) Implementation of evaluation of all standards is carried out by the foundation in general and the evaluation of each unit of education unit and the boarding party is responsible for the school principal and boarder of the dormitory. Regarding the implementation of learning evaluations in class is carried out every day, every week, every month, at the end of the semester which is evaluated by the teacher. implementation of all 12 JSIT standards, further studies, teacher training, teacher and student achievement, implementation of the learning process (lesson plans, evaluation sheets, literacy programs), the learning process in the dormitory (mentoring, assessment evaluation), extracurricular activities (mandatory, optional and boarding activities) 4) The implementation of evaluation of all standards is carried out by the foundation in general and the evaluation of each unit of education unit and the boarding party is responsible for the school principal and boarder of the dormitory. Regarding the implementation of learning evaluations in class is carried out every day, every week, every month, at the end of the semester which is evaluated by the teacher. the learning process in the dormitory (mentoring, evaluation evaluation), extracurricular activities (compulsory activities, choice and dormitory activities) 4) Evaluation of all standards is carried out by the foundation in general and the evaluation of each educational unit and the dormitory is responsible for the principal and boarder of the dormitory . Regarding the implementation of learning evaluations in class is

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KEYWORDS: Management, teacher quality and learning culture.

INTRODUCTION

The development of science is very much determined by the development of the world of education. The role of education which is very large and dynamic can determine the quality and knowledge of the community. The implementation of education in educational units has standards, through standards it will be easy to measure a quality educational institution's activities or not, quality education must be in line with the quality of quality teachers as well, because teachers play an important role in fostering a young generation who are ready to use, reliable, skilled and responsive to the future. In other words, ideally teachers are able to make a significant contribution in improving the quality of education nationally (Syafaruddin, 2008: 247). Curriculum management is an effort to succeed the expected educational goals. Development of existing curricula in Indonesia, now has undergone many changes. Curriculum changes are of course in accordance with the direction of the needs of educational institutions that are well designed in curriculum management. Among the factors that must be considered in managing the curriculum is a learning culture (Aziz, 2017: 197).

The planning of an organizational management system in Islamic education, is the first step that should be thoroughly noticed by the managers and managers of Islamic education. Therefore, the planning system that includes goal setting, target and education target should be based on the situation and conditions of the resource (Aziz et.al. 2019: 343). As a forum, education becomes a cultural process by humans from generation to generation taking a role in history, even though education is a cultural process of the present and makes a culture of the future. That is the importance of the function of education for individuals, families, communities and nations, so that the existence of a nation and the progress of its civilization are the results of the success of the implementation of education. Likewise, the history of destruction is the result of the failure of education to carry out its functions. The survival of a nation is not only in the physical aspect, but at the same time, psychologically, socially and culturally is the responsibility of education (Syafaruddin, 2017: 15).

Teachers as educators are the most urgent thing in educational institutions, teachers' competence and professionalism are low so that it has a negative impact on students, students will become weak in intelligence and personality, for that teachers always develop and create various competencies in their education field. The emergence of Integrated Islamic schools is a response to dissatisfaction with the national education system which is considered unable to answer the needs and challenges of the times, which are related to advances in science and technology.

Several research journals that have discussed the professionalism of teachers and Integrated Islamic Schools have been found. Some of them are written by Kurnaengsih (2015) regarding the Concept of an Integrated Islamic School. In his writing, he explained that the Integrated Islamic School emphasized the cultivation of religious subjects such as theology or faith, morals or morals, and practical worship. With Al-Banna's educational theory which aims to build character and morality of students with Islamic colors that are reflected in ways of thinking, attitudes and practices in everyday life. The purpose of education is not only to impart knowledge, both religious and general knowledge, but education is used as a way to form a complete Muslim personality both in terms of thinking and behavior.

Furthermore, regarding the Integrated Islamic School, the results of the dissertation research conducted by Magdalena with the title Transmission of Religious Fundamentalism Educational Ideology in the Integrated Islamic School of North Sumatra, 2017. This research examines the transmission of religious fundamentalism education ideology in the Integrated Islamic School (SIT) North Sumatra. This empirical study was carried out in three locations, namely SIT Al-Hijrah 2 Deli Serdang, SIT Bunayya Padangsidempuan, and SIT Al-Husnyain Panyabungan in the North Sumatra region. This study found variations in the delivery of education. The mapping of educational orientation in the delivery of education at SIT North Sumatra can be grouped into three, namely: 1) Tawheed education, 2) Moral education, and 3) Character education.

Furthermore, in the research of Lathifah Hanum (2016) the title Management of Educator Training for Education Personnel in Improving the Quality of Education in Man 2 Langsa Aceh. That training functions to improve the professional competence of educators and education personnel in order to achieve the ideal level, therefore it is necessary to receive continuous training as an effort to minimize obsolescence of knowledge in the current era of globalization, especially if teachers do not attend training and cannot gain access. new information Then educators and education personnel will be left behind. Then the data obtained that the management of educators and education staff training in improving the quality of education has been achieved well. Planning is carried out by involving all Madrasah personnel in the initial meeting of the school year, activities that have been

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planned have been carried out at MAN 2 Langsa and various places as needed. After it has been implemented, then it is the scope for obtaining feedback and as a guide to improve the quality of education and also to improve it in the future.

Research states that the form of teacher improvement is enhanced through training and coaching and planning is carried out involving the school as an assessment and evaluation for future education improvements. As for this dissertation, researchers revealed various forms of management in improving the quality of teachers starting from their welfare through certificates to continuous professional improvement through training and coaching by organizing workshops with various themes and work procedures involving financial planning as the determination of budget funds in its implementation. The principal involved the teacher organization through the KKG and MGMP in the procedures for procuring and calling participants for the implementation of training and seminars aimed at improving teacher quality.

Talking about the management of improving the quality of teachers in managing the classroom, International articles written by Jennifer Freeman, Brandi Simonsen, Donald E. Briere, Ashley S. MacSuga-Gage (2014) with the title Pre-Service Teacher Training in Classroom Management: A Review of State Accreditation Policy and Teacher Preparation Programs provides a dynamic explanation as a study of improving teacher management in schools. The article explains that:

Effective classroom management skills are essential for teachers. Unfortunately, many teachers do not receive adequate classroom management training prior to beginning their teaching careers and feel unprepared for the demands of managing student behavior in their classrooms. In this article, we describe (a) the number of states with state policy that requires pre-service teachers to receive instruction in evidence-based classroom management practices and (b) the extent to which teacher preparation programs provide this instruction for pre-service teachers. The results of this review indicate that although effective classroom management practices have been identified, a significant gap exists between the effective classroom management research base and requirements for teacher training. As a result,

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In terms of developing a learning culture in schools, Winarto, Lantip Diat Prasajo (2017), provides important points that must be implemented. Their research entitled Learning Culture Development Strategies in Schools explains that 1) a learning culture is formed and developed based on the analysis of the problems faced and the analysis of existing needs, 2) The learning culture of students is the attitudes and behaviors carried out by students in the educational process and learning. A learning culture is formed through the process of instilling values and norms in every program and activity that has been prepared by the school, 3) Management of a learning culture does not stand alone in a special program or activity, but is attached to every program and activity in every field, is at school.

The Integrated Islamic School (SIT) tries to pave a way to build quality education, one of which is by trying to create a balanced teaching between science and Islamic values in it, by integrating various components of Islamic activities that are able to form a strong and effective character education. The Integrated Islamic School (SIT) is currently one of the educational institutions that has received a wide response from the Indonesian Muslim community. This is evidenced by the increasing number of parents who send their children to various levels of SIT, from kindergarten, elementary, junior high to high school. Until now, there are thousands of Integrated Islamic schools that have gathered under the auspices of the Integrated Islamic School Network (JSIT).

Integrated Islamic Schoolin essence, it is a school that implements the concept of Islamic education based on the Al-Quran and Sunnah. In its application, the Integrated Islamic School is defined as a school that implements an approach to its implementation by combining general education and religious education into a curriculum. The Integrated Islamic School also emphasizes integration in learning methods so that it can optimize the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. The Integrated Islamic School also combines aqliyah, spiritual and religious education. In its implementation, it combines the involvement and active participation of the learning environment, namely schools, homes and communities (JSIT, 2014: 9).

Based on the background that has been described, the problem of this research is how to improve the management of teacher quality in the implementation of a student learning culture at an integrated Islamic school at the Al-Husnayain Mandailing Natal Indonesia Foundation. Then the researcher will analyze the planning, resource management, implementation, and evaluation of teacher quality improvement in the implementation of student learning culture at the Integrated Islamic School at the Al-Husnayain Mandailing Natal Indonesia Foundation.

As a basic function of the management section, that the management process is a combination of several groups of basic activities that are integrally related, which are carried out in general management, namely the planning process, the organizing

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process, the implementation process and the control process, in order to achieve an economic goal. In fact, the four processes are the result of a summary of the various opinions of practitioners and experts regarding management (Indartono, 2012: 8). Apart from these four management functions, there are still many experts who provide opinions regarding the management function.

METHOD

This study uses a qualitative method that seeks to extract information based on empirical data and facts in the field, and is logical, which means that it is acceptable to reason. Qualitative research is usually used in research in the field of social science (Hadi & Haryono, tt: 14). The qualitative research approach is also a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people and observable behavior (Moleong, 2005: 4).

According to Miles and Huberman, the data collected in this study is more decomposed in words than a series of numbers and the results are in the form of descriptions. However, this does not mean that qualitative research is free from reports in the form of numbers. One thing that is important in this qualitative research is not aimed at obtaining generalizations, but the data is analyzed inductively for patterns to look for the meaning of these patterns. Thus, the results of this study are idiographic, which emphasizes meaning in the context of time and space, then the data is taken directly from the natural setting: marked by the role of the researcher as a human instrument, digging up data and information.

To complement this qualitative approach, an educational method is used which seeks to study the management of improving the quality of teachers in the implementation of student learning culture at the Integrated Islamic School at the Al-Husnayain Mandailing Natal Foundation. As a key informant in the findings of novelty research, the researcher tries to explore situations and conditions in depth by finding various findings through observation, interviews and examining several documents for the completeness of the research followed by analyzing each problem finding, and providing an explanation of the result data. research. Because it is descriptive analytic, the data obtained are in the form of pictures, behavior and interview results which are then examined in the form of narrative descriptions. Therefore,

Sources of data in this study are: Key informants (key informants), are the Head of the Foundation, the principal and the teachers. Regarding secondary data sources, information was obtained from the school committee, parents of students, and the community (stakeholders). Places and events, where researchers obtain data, include the teaching and learning process, the decision-making process, teacher council meetings, school committee meetings, curriculum socialization and management, teacher quality development, the concept of educational services. Documents, among others, include meeting results, student learning outcomes, conditions of infrastructure, activities related to improving teacher quality and student achievement. This data is used to complement the results of interviews and observations of places and events.

RESULT AND DISCUSS

The Al Husnayain Integrated Islamic School (SIT) was founded in 2003, on an area of approximately 2 hectares, and is located in Pidoli Dolok Village, Panyabungan District, Mandailing Natal Regency, North Sumatra. The founder and concurrently chairman of SIT Al Husnayain is HA Riadi Husnan Hasibuan, the founder and supervisor of the Al Husnayain foundation which oversees and manages the Al Husnayain Integrated Islamic School.

The Al Husnayain Integrated Islamic School has a big opportunity to develop because of its strategic geographical location. The location of the school is in an area that is easily accessible by public transport and the environment is calm and comfortable. Behind that, all the threats to the Al Husnayain Integrated Islamic School stem from a shift in cultural values, namely the tendency of a metropolis life attitude that begins to hit student life, mimicking people's behavior with no clear background.

Therefore, character building activities and preserving cultural arts and sports are highly optimized through self-development activities. The existence of public school institutions and private institutions is a big competitor to the existence of this Foundation. Responding to this condition, the Al Husnayain Integrated Islamic School made real efforts in the form of improving the quality of educators and education personnel, completing facilities and infrastructure, establishing harmonious cooperation with parents / guardians of students and holding self-development activities taking into account the needs of students and the community.

Apart from that, considering the needs or desires of parents / guardians in the field of language and the Koran, in this case local content subjects of Tahfizhul Qur'an and Arabic are set at this Foundation. With this local content, it is hoped that the character of school members who care about the preservation of the Koran and the application of language will be formed.

In carrying out coaching students, the Al Husnayain Foundation applies the Boarding School system (boarding) except for Elementary Schools (SD), and the system is Fullday School. Students are nurtured 24 hours every day with various instructional and extracurricular activities that include fostering faith, worship, morals, science and technology and language. To date, the Al Husnayain Foundation has made progress both in terms of management and in terms of the number of students.

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Until now, the Al Husnayain Foundation continues to strive to develop and advance the student education system in terms of Intelligent Quotion (IQ), Emotional Quation (EQ), and Spiritual Quation (SQ), both internally and externally for the bright future of students and for the sake of progress. education both in Mandailing Natal Regency locally and nationally globally.

Planning for Teacher Quality Improvement in the Implementation of Student Learning Culture

Based on the planning theory implemented at the Al-Husnayain Foundation, it is good and systematic, for example in formulating plans, the foundation works closely with all school personnel, school principals, deputy school principals, administrative staff, teachers, dormitory supervisors. So it must make and have the main tasks that have been regulated in the main tasks and functions of the Al Husnayain foundation, namely: (1) having a school strategy plan, (2) 12 educational standards (3) the school education calendar, this is adjusted to the working days and learning hours for each class. -Each teacher (4) prepares learning tools (5) carries out evaluation of learning programs consisting of teacher teaching evaluations, evaluation of student learning outcomes and evaluation of curriculum achievement (6) learning in dormitories,

Teachers who do not make or implement learning administration planning are not allowed to enter the classroom. The school principal continues to pay attention to teachers who have not finished completing learning tools.

Organizing (Arranging) Resources for Improving Teacher Quality in the Implementation of Student Learning Culture

Before explaining the nature of organizing as a management function, it is necessary to first state the meaning of an organization which is the container for all managerial activities, including organizing. Organization is the cooperation of two or more people in one coordinated situation to achieve the desired result. In the organization there are a number of people both as managers and as members, there are structures, goals, rules and procedures. People who carry out this management are called managers, and those who carry out practical work are members, personnel, subordinates or followers (Syafaruddin, 2017: 82-83).

One organization consists of several elements, namely: 1. There is a group of people, 2. There is a division of labor or specialization in the organization, 3. Collaboration where separate activities are coordinated, 4. There are common goals to be achieved through coordinated cooperation (Syafaruddin, 2017: 83). For the continuity of organizational functions, there are several principles in its management, namely: 1). Unity of command 2). 3) surveillance range. Division of labor, and 4). Departmentalization. Organizing is the second management function and is a strategic step towards realizing an organizational plan. According to Winadi (1990), organizing is a work process that is divided into components that can be handled and activities that coordinate the results achieved to achieve certain goals.

Organizing and organizing carried out by the foundation and assisted by all personnel at the Al Husnayain Foundation, the foundation in this case has an important role as a decision maker. All regulations that have been agreed upon can be seen in the strategic plan, main duties and functions and all regulations that have been established as references and benchmarks in running an organization, in this case at the Al Husnayain educational foundation. This foundation has a healthy and good organizational culture in terms of cooperation in realizing the vision and mission of the educational foundation under the auspices of JSIT.

The bottom-up coordination enables the foundation to prove that the foundation owners are able and continue to strive to develop this school from year to year to the fullest. It is proven by joining to become part of JSIT in North Sumatra, making this school continue to be better and following the current era of the development of Integrated Islamic Schools with nuances *boarding school*. The foundation carries out comprehensive supervision and is assisted by the principal in each education unit to oversee the process of improving the quality of teachers in all fields, supervises the learning process, holds meetings to resolve any problems or violations.

In the implementation of the organizing function, foundations and school principals show their democratic nature by giving confidence to the curriculum team, boarding coaches, student affairs, extracurricular activities, self-development etc. which are formed according to the needs of the school to participate in carrying out the tasks mandated by the principal in accordance with predetermined main tasks and functions. This will provide input to all school personnel that one another must cooperate with each other. Thus, the goals to be achieved will be easier to achieve.

Implementation of Teacher Quality Improvement in the Implementation of Student Learning Culture

The implementation of the work program that has been planned in the previous stages is then tried out in the implementation and management, while always making adjustments to the field situation and student characteristics, both school development, intellectual development of teachers and students, and building emotional and character in all components of education, namely school, family and community. All school programs will be carried out well and maximally if there is good cooperation from the foundation, school principals, teachers, students, parents, and the community.

The implementation of the teacher quality improvement program can be carried out according to the schedule to be determined such as the implementation of education and training training (Diklat). Teacher competency improvement can be done through in-service training programs. Training implies that after participating in the training the teacher will be motivated to improve performance, learning methods or refresher their knowledge and information. General training is defined as an activity to

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improve the mastery of various skills and techniques for carrying out certain work in a very short time. Syamsul Rizal et.al (2020) stated that the objectives of this training program were to: a) Improve the quality of human resources; b) Creating interactions between teachers; c) Strengthen the sense of kinship and togetherness between educators;

After the implementation of the teacher quality improvement program was carried out, it had a profound impact on the professionalism of the teachers themselves. Syamsul Rizal et.al (2020) states that the impacts felt include:

1. Increased motivation and morale, teachers are more confident, understand better the meaning of being an educator, are more responsible in assignments and time and are more loving and caring for students and are more creative in teaching. There is always a place to channel their various obstacles and other teachers respond to them so that the teacher can get solutions and can make continuous improvements. The teachers have broad insights and can immediately be put into practice.
2. Teachers can be role models for students. Exemplary will greatly affect learning outcomes, and the quality of learning outcomes is strongly influenced by the quality of exemplary shown by the teachers.
3. The program for improving the quality of teachers continuously is an effort to develop competency aspects of education personnel with the aim that teachers continue to develop in line with developments in science and technology. Improving the quality of teachers has always been a priority, because this effort is based on the reason that the main indicator of school success is the ability to carry out teaching and learning activities effectively and efficiently in accordance with the demands of the curriculum and to prepare graduates that meet current and future development needs.
4. The role that is strategic and is the key to the success of achieving school institutional goals can be carried out by teachers. Teachers are managers of teaching and learning activities for their students. Teaching and learning activities will run effectively if there are teachers who match the needs of the school in terms of numbers, qualifications, and fields of expertise.
5. Teacher competencies such as personality competence, social competence, pedagogical competence and professional competence can be developed well. When carried out continuously, the educator or teacher will get an optimal quality improvement process. The teacher also realizes that what they already have, if not developed again, they will be left behind.
6. Law of the Republic of Indonesia number 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system has stated that the position of teacher as an educator is a professional position. For this reason, professional teachers are required to continuously develop themselves in accordance with the times, science, technology, and the needs of society, including the need for quality human resources who have the capability to be able to compete in regional, national and international forums .

The positive impact of implementing the continuous teacher quality improvement program has been stated above which can be the reason that all educational institutions must see that teachers are human capital which is a valuable asset that will make a major contribution to the achievement of educational goals, which are sustainable and lead to progress to better or superior.

The implementation of all programs is in accordance with the 12 standards set by JSIT and the foundation. The implementation of this program begins with the foundation coordinating with school principals, teachers and related administrative staff, especially related to the implementation of teacher quality improvement activities by making learning improvements by involving teachers as training participants and providing opportunities for teachers who wish to continue their education to a higher level. Middle and high school principals are currently attending postgraduate education at Padang State University (UNP). Training is carried out by all teachers without exception and this activity is carried out by the foundation, JSIT, and the Panyabungan Education Office.

Increasing the quality of teachers will also provide positive improvements to the implementation of learning in students. So that there is an awareness of students to do independent learning, because in addition to learning activities at school, students also have to follow the rules in the dormitory, starting from getting up in the morning to going to sleep. Elementary school students also have student activity sheets that are filled in by parents. All student activities are supervised by the classroom teacher and dormitory coaches and parents. The Tahfiz program, science and mathematics are independent learning cultures that have been built up in students, as evidenced by the awards won by students when participating in competitions. The champions that are currently being won are still at the district level, especially elementary school students.

The work program that has been compiled and implemented must be supervised by the foundation, then the foundation will authorize the principal to supervise teachers and staff in each unit. Supervision is the final part of the management function. The controlled management function is planning, organizing, directing and controlling itself.

In carrying out this supervisory function, the principal carries out direct supervision of the work of teachers and units under them. The aim is to find out which personnel experience obstacles in carrying out their duties, the types of obstacles experienced and what solutions are best given to re-launch the obstructed work. Especially for teacher performance, this supervision is carried out through classroom supervision and is broader (comprehensive). The principal in terms of supervision is

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very good because he continues to supervise the class and always reminds them to continue to attend the routine weekly recitation, and give advice to really carry out their duties (mandate).

Implementation of Evaluation of Teacher Quality Improvement in the Implementation of Student Learning Culture

Evaluation is an act of consideration based on a set of agreed and accountable criteria. Evaluation is a type of evaluation carried out to reveal what the impact is and who is affected by the planning and implementation of teacher quality improvement management carried out in Integrated Islamic Schools. This is done with the aim of knowing the expected results or benefits and impacts that have been achieved. Evaluation will have the impact of paying greater attention to the output and impact of policies. The evaluation that will be carried out to see various things according to Ana Jauharul Islam, et.al (2014) includes the following:

1. Determine whether the program has had the desired impact on individuals, households and institutions.
2. Assess whether these impacts are related to program interventions.
3. Explore the unexpected both positive and negative consequences.
4. Issues highlighted were how the program affected program participants and whether the improvement in participants' conditions was really due to the program or other factors.

The implementation of this evaluation is focused on management functions carried out by foundations and school principals in the context of implementing teacher quality improvement management and implementing student learning culture. In its implementation, there are management functions that cannot be carried out properly and efficiently because the current conditions are currently in the Covid 19 pandemic, unlike normal conditions, even though the learning process continues according to the schedule and curriculum, even the lesson learned by the teacher is getting the knowledge of online learning training. by using interesting learning animations, etc., it's just that the delay of students entering the dormitory makes the teacher less optimal in instilling character in students. But related to independent learning, it becomes more developed in students to learn independently and be more creative,

The implementation of evaluation of all standards is carried out by the foundation in general and the evaluation of each education unit and the boarding house is responsible for the principal and the boarder of the dormitory. Regarding the implementation of learning evaluations in class, it is carried out every day, every week, every month, at the end of the semester and every year it must be reported and student progress must also be reported at every teacher meeting. This assessment is inseparable from three domains, namely cognitive, affective and psychomotor and leads to curriculum standards.

The implementation of the evaluation function in Islam is regulated in the Koran and Hadith. Evaluation is one component of the Islamic education system that must be carried out systematically and planned as a tool to measure success or targets to be achieved in the management process of Islamic education. Evaluation in a very strategic position, because the results of evaluation activities can be used as input to improve educational activities. Islamic teachings also pay great attention to this evaluation. In the Al Qur'an and hadith, it informs that the work of evaluating humans is an important task in a series of educational processes that have been carried out by every element of the school.

Some terms can be used as an indication of the meaning of direct evaluation or just a tool or process in evaluation. This is based on the assumption that the Al-Qur'an and Hadith are the principles and principles of Islamic education management, while for operation it depends on *ijtihad*. The term evaluation at the next stage is more oriented towards the meaning of "interpretation or giving decisions on education". Every educational action is based on a specific educational plan, objectives, materials, tools and environment. Based on this component, the role of assessment is needed to determine the extent to which educational success has been achieved. From this understanding, the process of implementing the assessment is more emphasized at the end of the action.

CONCLUSION

Based on the various research findings above, this research can be summarized as follows:

1. Planning to improve the quality of teachers in the implementation of student learning culture at the Integrated Islamic School at the Al-Husnayain Mandailing Natal Foundation has been carried out well according to the education standards of the Integrated Islamic School and according to the Ministry of Education and Culture's curriculum then integrated with the pesantren regulations. Planning in the form of work programs, regulations that have been agreed upon at the foundation meeting, school principals and teachers. Each teacher prepares the learning administration before teaching. This plan was agreed upon in a meeting attended by the foundation, school principals, and teachers. The decision of the meeting entirely boils down to the foundation. Because the foundation has full authority on every plan that will be carried out by the academic community in this foundation. So all activities in this foundation must have permission from the foundation. Whereas in learning planning the principal acts as a manager and works closely with field teachers and school administration staff. Every subject teacher must create and own an administration and learning tools. Both teachers in schools and teachers as boarders.

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2. In the implementation of the organizing management function, foundations and school principals demonstrate their democratic nature by giving confidence to the curriculum team, boarders, student affairs, extracurricular activities, self-development etc. to participate in carrying out the duties of the principal in accordance with the given authority. This will provide input to all school personnel that each other must cooperate with each other. Thus, the goals to be achieved will be easier to achieve. Organizing and organizing carried out by the foundation and assisted by all personnel at the Al Husnayain Foundation, the foundation in this case has an important role as a decision maker. All regulations that have been agreed upon are contained in the strategic plan, main duties and functions, the work program and all the regulations that have been established become a reference and benchmark in running an organization. The Al Husnayain education foundation has a healthy and good organizational culture in terms of teamwork in realizing the vision and mission of the school under the auspices of JSIT.
3. The school principal in terms of implementation (direction and implementation) of improving the quality of teachers and implementing a learning culture has gone well because the foundation fully supports both morale and facilities so that the implementation of training programs and the creation of a student learning culture goes according to expectations. Teacher training is carried out by the foundation, JSIT, and the Education Office. Training is compulsory for all teachers. Teachers are given the opportunity to continue to higher levels of education, teachers who have been certified are facilitated in fulfilling teacher performance reports. Supporting a learning culture is evidenced by the many activities in schools that require students to study independently, for example activities in dormitories with lots of learning rules, school and family literacy, hifzhil quran, libraries, science olympiad activities etc. All activities allow students to continue to learn and be independent. The direction given by the foundation and the principal regarding the implementation of their respective duties and responsibilities. This briefing is an elaboration of the vision, mission and goals of the school so that teachers are directed to carry out all programs that have been compiled based on the applicable Integrated Islamic school standards to achieve the goals that have been formulated. In the implementation of learning the teacher chooses methods and props that are easy and attractive, learning is not only in the classroom but also outside the classroom such as the method of learning to develop morals through direction, habituation, and example (Learning by Qudwah), development of logic and creativity through Experiential Learning (involving students to experience real experiences),
4. The implementation of evaluation is the key to future improvement. Before carrying out this evaluation, the foundation continues to supervise 12 education standards, whether it is running according to the applicable regulations. The implementation of the evaluation is aimed at all school components in the implementation of the management function of the foundation as a leader and in coordination with the principal, in particular the management of improving the quality of teachers and the implementation of a learning culture that is considered good. The basis for the assessment is (1) three management functions, namely planning, implementation and evaluation can be carried out by foundations and principals properly, (2) improving teacher quality continues to be evaluated both in increasing teacher competence and learning tools as well as teacher activeness in fostering student extracurricular activities. , both in dormitories and monitoring of children's learning activities at home for elementary students, (3) Each teacher also reports the results of student assessment evaluations, namely daily, weekly, monthly, semester and annual evaluations, and these assessments cannot be separated from three domains, namely cognitive , affective and psychomotor. This evaluation is carried out to determine the level of children's development continuously through the Report Book (Liaison, Development of Monthly Student Learning Achievement, Worship Achievements, Prayer Agenda, Competency Achievements of the Koran) implementation of the evaluation is also carried out so that it can be improved for the future and for the advancement of education. at the Al Husnayain Indonesia Foundation. semester and yearly, and the assessment is inseparable from three domains, namely cognitive, affective and psychomotor. This evaluation is carried out to determine the level of children's development continuously through the Report Book (Liaison, Development of Monthly Student Learning Achievement, Worship Achievements, Prayer Agenda, Competency Achievements of the Koran), the evaluation is also carried out so that it can be improved for the future and for the advancement of education at the Al Husnayain Indonesia Foundation. semester and yearly, and the assessment is inseparable from three domains, namely cognitive, affective and psychomotor. This evaluation is carried out to determine the level of children's development continuously through the Report Book (Liaison, Development of Monthly Student Learning Achievement, Worship Achievements, Prayer Agenda, Competency Achievements of the Koran) implementation of the evaluation is also carried out so that it can be improved for the future and for educational advancement at the Al Husnayain Indonesia Foundation.

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